

Tutor Performance in Distance Education in the Islands (Case Study: Open University, Indonesia)

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ABSTRACT : *This research is a descriptive study that aims to determine the performance of tutors in distance education in the islands. The study population was 57 tutors who were in charge of giving tutorials in 2019.1 at UPBJJ-UT Ternate. All of them serve as research samples. The research data were obtained from a combination of student assessment results for each tutor he attended, as well as the results of observational assessments conducted by the Ternate UPBJJ-UT monitoring officer. From the results of the overall data analysis, it can be concluded that the Evaluation Results of Tutor's performance at UPBJJ-UT Ternate are all in the good category so it is recommended to continue assignments in the coming semester.*

KEYWORDS: *Performance, Distance education, Tutor, Islands*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the Distance Learning System (SBJJ) as applied by the Open University (UT), students are required to be able to manage their learning independently. The independent learning method requires students to learn on their own initiative. With this initiative, students will try to find the learning resources they need. From this learning source, students then try themselves to understand the content of the lessons available in all learning resources they get.

Wardani (2000) suggests that one way to encourage students to improve their ability to learn independently is through tutorials. With tutorials (face to face or online), students are expected to be able to interact with tutors and peers so that they can overcome learning problems, especially regarding the understanding of teaching materials provided (Adji and Rokhiyah, 2011). Even more than that, this tutorial is expected to accelerate the process of teaching and learning, increase understanding, expand vision and foster independence in student learning.

Considering the role of tutors is very important in the tutorial process, efforts to develop the quality of tutors are also important for UT to do. But the problem is, tutors at UT are professionals / lecturers / practitioners in their respective fields who come from outside UT. So at the beginning of carrying out the task do not recognize the concept of the tutorial. For example, a lecturer from another university, when he was a tutor, found it difficult to distinguish himself who had changed functions, no longer as a lecturer but as a tutor. If in a university that holds face-to-face lectures, lecturers are a source of knowledge. But at UT, tutors are no longer a source of knowledge, but rather function as facilitators and motivators to take students towards independent learning. The source of knowledge has been provided by UT, through modules that have been prepared by the lecturer in charge of the course.

This study is a follow-up study from previous researchers Dina Thaib, et al (2004), Herman (2010), Ruganda et al (2012), Amani and Anita (2014) about the performance of face-to-face tutors at UT. But in research, everything is done in urban areas, which of course has different characteristics from the regions, especially in the islands. For example, there are differences in the availability of tutorial facilities, tutorial locations, available human resources, and most importantly the motivation of participants and tutors. Based on this reason, in this study, the focus of the study was on the islands, in the offices of the Open University Distance Learning Program (UPBJJ-UT) Ternate.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are several terms in Indonesian that are often used to mean performance, such as work results, impact and work performance. Gomes (2003), defines performance as a record of the results resulting from a particular job function or activity during a certain period. Whereas Ilyas (1999), defines performance as the appearance of personal work both in quality and quantity in an organization.

Performance appraisal is a way to measure the contribution of individual members to the organization (Gomes, 2003). The purpose of performance appraisal in general can be divided into two types, namely to Reward past performance and motivate future performance improvement.

The benefits of information obtained from performance appraisal are in the interests of salary giving, salary increases, promotions, and determination of task specialization. Viewed from the reference point for assessment, performance appraisal can be divided into three types consisting of:

1. Performance appraisal is based on results, where the formulation of work implementation is based on measurement of final results.
2. Performance appraisal is based on behavior, which measures the implementation of individual work in teams in an effort to achieve goals, not just the final result.
3. Performance appraisal is based on appraisal, which is an appraisal or evaluation of workers based on a description of certain behaviors, such as: quantity and quality of work, knowledge and skills at work, creativity, loyalty, trust and enthusiasm for work, and personality.

Some good criteria in measuring performance are if the output that is produced is reliable, realistic, representative, and predictable (As'ad, 1999). Meanwhile, according to Meier (2002), the most commonly considered criteria are quality, quantity, time spent, position held, attendance and safety in carrying out work duties.

Hypothesis Development

The success of the tutorial process carried out by a tutor is inseparable from its performance. In implementing tutorial activities, tutors are expected to have the ability to use various tutorials, provide feedback and feedback on assignments performed by students, guide students to be able to learn effectively, and provide time for student consultation (Amani and Anita, 2014).

At UT, tutors' performance evaluations are regulated in the Distance Education Management procedures issued by the UT Quality Assurance Center (Pusmintas). In the JKOP BB02 procedure, the procedure for selecting and evaluating Non-UT academic staff states that the Tutor is an academic staff that facilitates the learning process of students with an emphasis on mastery and deepening of course material in accordance with teaching materials (Pusmintas UT, 2013). Teacher criteria for undergraduate programs are:

1. Lecturers in the field of study relevant to the subject who will get the tutorial
2. Teachers are required to have a master's degree, in a field of study relevant to the subject who will get a tutorial
3. Practitioners, at least 5 years of experience with expertise relevant to the subject will get a tutorial.

While the criteria for postgraduate tutors, namely lecturers holding doctorates in the field of study relevant to the subject matter to be taught.

In JKOP BB03 procedure on Tutorial Procedure, tutor performance evaluation is conducted by students and UPBJJ-UT. Students assess the quality of tutorials in the classroom, while UPBJJ-UT assesses the implementation process, ranging from discipline, suitability of tutorial procedures to the completeness of report files. From the results of tutor evaluations by students and UPBJJ-UT, recommendations will be generated: (1) reassigned, (2) still gets assignments with notes or warnings to tutors to improve their performance, or (3) no longer assigned (Pusmintas UT, 2013).

This research was conducted using a tutor performance measurement tool that has been provided by Pusmintas UT, with the initial hypothesis, namely: The results of tutor performance evaluations at UPBJJ-UT Ternate are all in the good category so they get recommendations to continue teaching in the next semester

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a descriptive study that aims to determine the performance of tutors in distance education in the archipelago. The study population was 57 tutors who were in charge of giving tutorials in 2019.1 semester at UPBJJ-UT Ternate. All of them serve as research samples.

The research data were obtained from a combination of student assessment results for each tutor he attended, as well as the results of observational assessments conducted by the Ternate UPBJJ-UT monitoring officer. Assessment of instructor instrument performance by students in the form of questionnaires. Consists of 14 question items with a weight value of each item, namely 1 (Strongly Disagree), 2 (Disagree), 3 (Agree), and 4 (Strongly Agree). Tutor evaluation questionnaire scores by students are categorized into 3 categories: (1) Score ≥ 3.00 , (2) $2.50 \leq \text{Score} < 3.00$, and (3) Score < 2.50 .

Table 1. Tutor aspects evaluated by students

No.	Aspects of the Tutor being evaluated	Assessment			
		1	2	3	4
1	At the first meeting, explain the tutorial rules clearly				
2	Each meeting clearly outlines the aims and benefits of the course material				
3	Mastering subject matter that is diutoriakan				
4	Gives enrichment of material and examples that are easy to understand				
5	Describe the material systematically and interestingly				
6	Use language that is easy to understand				
7	Be polite in implementing the tutorial				
8	Motivate students to participate actively				
9	Manage the discussion interestingly so that all participants actively participate				
10	Provide equal opportunities for students to answer questions in the tutorial				
11	Give tutorial assignments at 3rd, 5th, 7th meeting				
12	Give feedback about the results of student assignments in detail so that students know the advantages and disadvantages				
13	Invite students to summarize the essence of the material presented				
14	Start and end tutorial meetings on time				

Source: Pasmintas UT, 2013

Whereas tutor evaluations by UPBJJ-UT Ternate in the form of observation sheets relating to the completeness of the administrative requirements of the tutor, discipline in the tutorial and the appropriateness of the tutorial reporting results. The observations are grouped into 3 categories, namely: (1) Meet all aspects of tutor assessment, (2) Meet aspects 1 and 2 tutor ratings, (3) Do not meet aspects 1 and 2 tutor ratings.

Table 2. Observation table of UPBJJ-UT on Tutors

No.	Tutor Assessment Aspects	Qualify	
		Yas	No
1.	Send a recapitulation of the value in the specified format on time		
2.	Send sample results from 3 tutorial assignments that have been rated and feedback (highest and lowest assignment scores)		
3.	Carry out the tutorial according to a predetermined schedule (8 x meetings)		
4.	Submit the Tutorial Activity design		
5.	Record tutorial meetings on the Tutorial Meeting Notes form consistently		

Source: Pasmintas UT, 2013

The results of the assessment are further processed and produce a form of follow-up recommendations, with the following details:

Table 3. Suggested criteria on the results of tutor assessments by students and UPBJJ-UT

Student Evaluation Results from Tutors	Results of UPBJJ-UT observations on tutors	Recommendation
Score $\geq 3,00$	Meet all aspects of tutor assessment	Reassigned the following semester
Score $\geq 3,00$	Meet aspects 1 and 2 of tutor assessment	Reassigned with written warnings about administrative fulfillment in the following semester
Score $\geq 3,00$	Does not meet aspects 1 and 2 of tutor assessment	No longer assigned
$2,50 \leq \text{Score} < 3,00$	Meet all aspects of tutor assessment	Reassigned with written warnings about fulfilling competencies
$2,50 \leq \text{Score} < 3,00$	Meet aspects 1 and 2 of tutor assessment	Reassigned with written warnings about fulfilling competence and administration
$2,50 \leq \text{Score} < 3,00$	Does not meet aspects 1 and 2 of tutor assessment	Reassigned the following semester

Student Evaluation Results from Tutors	Results of UPBJJ-UT observations on tutors	Recommendation
Score $< 2,50$	Meet all aspects of tutor assessment	Reassigned with written warnings about fulfilling competencies
Score $< 2,50$	Meet aspects 1 and 2 of tutor assessment	No longer assigned
Score $< 2,50$	Does not meet aspects 1 and 2 of tutor assessment	No longer assigned i

Source: Pusmintas UT, 2013

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the distance learning system, tutorials are learning aids for students, so the application of the tutorial is different from lectures. At UT, this tutorial is only held for 8 meetings, where the role of the tutor is to help students understand the subject matter available in modules that have been distributed to students before implementing the tutor. thus students are expected to have studied at home, so that during the tutorial, students will deepen the material being studied. After processing the data, the results of the tutor's evaluation are as follows:

Table 4. Data processing results in Tutor evaluation

No	Evaluation result		Recommendation	Number of Tutors
	Student	UPBJJ-UT		
1	Score $\geq 3,00$	Meet all aspects of tutor assessment	Reassigned the following semester	48
2	Score $\geq 3,00$	Meet aspects 1 and 2 of tutor assessment	Reassigned with written warnings about administrative fulfillment in the following semester	0
3	Score $\geq 3,00$	Does not meet aspects 1 and 2 of tutor assessment	No longer assigned	0
4	$2,50 \leq \text{Score} < 3,00$	Meet all aspects of tutor assessment	Reassigned with written warnings about fulfilling competencies	9

5	$2,50 \leq \text{Score} < 3,00$	Meet aspects 1 and 2 of tutor assessment	Reassigned with written warnings about fulfilling competence and administration	0
6	$2,50 \leq \text{Score} < 3,00$	Does not meet aspects 1 and 2 of tutor assessment	Reassigned the following semester	0
7	Score < 2,50	Meet all aspects of tutor assessment	Reassigned with written warnings about fulfilling competencies	0
8	Score < 2,50	Meet aspects 1 and 2 of tutor assessment	No longer assigned	0
9	Score < 2,50	Does not meet aspects 1 and 2 of tutor assessment	No longer assigned i	0
Total				57

Source: Research data processing results

In table 2 above, it can be seen that from the evaluation of 57 tutors by students, the results are divided into 2 categories namely 48 tutors into category 1 which scores ≥ 3.00 and 9 tutors fall into category 2 which is $2.50 \leq \text{Score} < 3.00$. While based on observations of UPBJJ-UT Ternate, all tutors have been categorized in (1) "fulfilling all aspects of tutor assessment".

Thus it can be said that all tutors have performed well so that the recommendation results can be used again to be assigned as tutors in the following semester. The results of the assessment on each aspect of the tutorial by students can be presented in the following table:

Tabel 5. Details of scores on each Aspect Tutor evaluated by students

Respon- dents	Average scores on each aspect of the teacher being evaluated														Average
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	
1	3,40	3,50	3,50	3,50	3,80	3,50	3,60	3,60	3,60	3,80	3,80	3,80	3,50	3,50	3,60
2	3,58	3,67	3,83	3,58	3,67	3,42	3,58	3,42	3,42	3,50	3,92	3,42	3,58	3,67	3,67
3	3,70	3,80	3,90	3,50	3,60	3,40	3,50	3,50	3,50	3,40	4,00	3,60	3,50	3,30	3,59
4	3,77	3,85	3,85	3,54	3,46	3,62	3,54	3,62	3,46	3,00	3,92	3,38	3,54	3,46	3,57
5	3,64	3,82	3,55	3,36	3,55	3,18	3,55	3,55	3,73	3,55	4,00	3,55	3,36	3,36	3,55
6	3,53	3,53	3,53	4,00	3,53	3,82	3,82	3,53	3,35	3,06	4,00	3,06	3,24	3,71	3,55
7	3,36	3,64	3,45	3,64	3,55	3,55	3,73	3,73	3,64	3,27	3,82	3,36	3,45	3,45	3,55
8	3,45	3,64	3,64	3,45	3,45	3,55	3,55	3,64	3,45	3,18	3,91	3,36	3,45	3,27	3,50
9	3,45	3,64	3,64	3,45	3,45	3,55	3,55	3,64	3,45	3,18	3,91	3,36	3,45	3,27	3,50
10	3,30	3,40	3,30	3,50	3,80	3,40	3,50	3,50	3,70	3,60	3,80	3,60	3,30	3,30	3,50
11	3,68	3,54	3,62	3,85	3,54	3,54	3,62	3,46	3,15	3,15	3,77	3,15	3,23	3,69	3,50
12	3,45	3,73	3,36	3,73	3,36	3,73	3,73	3,36	3,09	3,18	3,73	3,36	3,45	3,64	3,49
13	3,30	3,40	3,30	3,40	3,70	3,40	3,50	3,50	3,60	3,70	3,80	3,60	3,30	3,30	3,49
14	3,50	3,75	3,25	3,75	3,25	3,58	3,58	3,33	3,17	3,17	3,75	3,42	3,42	3,67	3,47
15	3,46	3,54	3,69	3,38	3,31	3,62	3,38	3,62	3,31	3,00	3,92	3,23	3,54	3,31	3,45
16	3,30	3,20	3,50	3,60	3,50	3,30	3,30	3,50	3,50	3,40	3,50	3,20	3,40	3,70	3,42
17	3,30	3,20	3,50	3,60	3,50	3,30	3,30	3,50	3,50	3,40	3,50	3,20	3,40	3,70	3,42
18	3,40	3,50	3,20	3,30	3,60	3,30	3,40	3,40	3,50	3,60	3,70	3,50	3,20	3,20	3,41
19	3,31	3,46	3,46	3,46	3,31	3,62	3,54	3,54	3,31	3,08	3,77	3,15	3,46	3,31	3,41
20	3,31	3,46	3,46	3,46	3,31	3,62	3,54	3,54	3,31	3,08	3,77	3,15	3,46	3,31	3,41
21	3,51	3,46	3,46	3,85	3,38	3,54	3,62	3,38	3,08	2,92	3,85	2,92	3,15	3,62	3,41
22	3,38	3,46	3,54	3,38	3,31	3,54	3,38	3,54	3,31	3,08	3,69	3,23	3,46	3,31	3,40
23	3,40	3,40	3,40	3,40	3,40	3,40	3,40	3,60	3,00	3,00	3,80	3,40	3,40	3,60	3,40
24	3,36	3,45	3,55	3,36	3,27	3,55	3,45	3,45	3,27	3,09	3,82	3,18	3,45	3,27	3,40
25	3,18	3,36	3,45	3,36	3,36	3,45	3,45	3,64	3,45	3,09	3,73	3,18	3,45	3,27	3,39
26	3,18	3,64	3,09	3,64	3,09	3,45	3,45	3,45	3,27	3,27	3,91	3,27	3,27	3,45	3,39
27	3,47	3,60	3,20	3,53	3,20	3,40	3,47	3,20	3,13	3,20	3,73	3,33	3,33	3,53	3,38
28	3,27	3,27	3,27	3,27	3,27	3,27	3,27	3,45	3,18	3,18	3,82	3,27	3,27	3,45	3,32
29	3,33	3,47	3,13	3,40	3,13	3,27	3,53	2,93	3,13	3,40	3,60	3,27	3,27	3,40	3,30
30	3,33	3,47	3,13	3,40	3,13	3,27	3,53	2,93	3,13	3,40	3,60	3,27	3,27	3,40	3,30
31	3,33	3,47	3,13	3,40	3,13	3,27	3,53	2,93	3,13	3,40	3,60	3,27	3,27	3,40	3,30
32	3,33	3,47	3,13	3,40	3,13	3,27	3,53	2,93	3,13	3,40	3,60	3,27	3,27	3,40	3,30

33	3,27	3,27	3,27	3,27	3,27	3,27	3,27	3,45	3,00	3,00	3,73	3,27	3,27	3,45	3,29
34	3,20	3,33	3,07	3,33	3,07	3,20	3,40	2,93	3,13	3,33	3,47	3,20	3,20	3,43	3,24
35	3,08	3,31	3,23	3,31	3,08	3,46	3,31	3,38	3,08	2,92	3,62	2,92	3,31	3,08	3,22
36	3,39	3,22	3,35	3,09	3,09	3,26	3,09	3,26	3,09	2,83	4,00	2,91	3,09	3,09	3,20
37	3,17	3,25	3,08	3,25	3,08	3,17	3,50	2,75	3,08	3,42	3,33	3,17	3,17	3,25	3,19
38	3,48	3,43	3,43	3,43	2,57	3,43	3,43	3,00	2,57	2,96	3,57	2,96	2,96	3,43	3,19
39	3,23	3,00	3,47	3,33	3,07	3,07	3,27	2,87	3,07	3,33	3,40	3,00	3,27	3,20	3,18
40	2,92	3,08	3,15	3,15	3,15	3,54	3,31	3,54	3,15	2,62	3,46	2,77	3,38	3,15	3,17
41	3,27	3,27	3,18	3,27	3,00	3,09	3,18	3,18	2,73	2,82	3,45	3,09	3,09	3,18	3,13
42	3,27	3,27	3,18	3,27	3,00	3,09	3,18	3,18	2,73	2,82	3,45	3,09	3,09	3,18	3,13
43	3,30	2,90	3,10	3,10	3,20	3,00	3,20	3,10	3,30	3,20	3,20	3,00	3,10	3,10	3,13
44	2,87	3,48	3,00	2,83	3,00	3,00	2,61	2,83	3,22	2,83	3,61	3,22	3,22	3,22	3,07
45	3,22	2,91	3,17	3,17	2,83	3,17	3,17	3,00	2,83	2,70	3,83	2,70	2,70	3,17	3,04
46	3,18	2,88	3,18	3,18	2,82	3,18	3,18	3,00	2,82	2,71	3,76	2,65	2,71	3,18	3,03
47	3,07	2,80	2,93	3,73	2,80	2,80	3,13	3,00	2,67	2,93	3,53	2,67	2,80	3,20	3,01
48	3,00	3,00	3,00	3,00	3,00	3,00	3,00	3,00	3,00	3,00	3,00	3,00	3,00	3,00	3,00
49	3,29	3,29	3,29	3,29	2,53	3,00	3,29	2,88	2,35	2,59	3,29	2,65	2,59	3,12	2,96
50	3,13	3,13	3,33	3,20	2,73	2,87	2,93	2,93	2,87	3,07	3,20	2,47	2,40	2,87	2,94
51	3,26	3,13	3,13	3,13	2,61	2,87	3,13	2,91	2,52	2,52	3,52	2,61	2,52	3,04	2,92
52	3,31	3,00	2,23	2,46	3,46	2,23	2,38	3,15	3,15	3,38	3,23	2,77	2,92	3,00	2,91
53	3,14	3,15	3,38	3,23	2,77	2,92	3,31	3,00	2,23	2,46	3,46	2,23	2,38	3,00	2,91
54	2,64	3,27	3,00	2,55	2,73	3,00	3,00	2,91	3,09	2,82	3,45	2,55	2,82	2,55	2,88
55	2,40	3,20	3,00	2,47	2,73	3,07	2,93	2,73	3,07	2,67	3,33	2,53	2,80	2,53	2,82
56	3,30	3,00	2,23	2,46	3,46	2,23	3,31	3,00	2,23	2,46	3,46	2,23	2,38	3,00	2,77
57	3,05	3,08	3,08	3,08	2,54	2,54	3,08	2,77	2,23	2,23	3,08	2,23	2,23	2,77	2,71
Average	3,29	3,36	3,29	3,33	3,20	3,26	3,35	3,26	3,13	3,09	3,64	3,09	3,17	3,29	

Source: Research data processing results

The highest value of the tutor assessment aspect lies in the assignment aspect which is 3.64. Where students assess that the tutor is timely to schedule assignments to students at meetings 3, 5 and 7. This assignment is an evaluation material whose results can be used as input for tutors and students to find out how far students have mastered the material. The results of this study are the same as Amani and Anita (2014) at UPBJJ-UT Banjarmasin, that the average performance of UPBJJ-UT tutors on the aspect of giving tutorial assignments at meetings 3, 5, 7 has been categorized as Good.

While the lowest value aspect of tutor assessment lies in the aspect of Giving equal opportunity to each student to answer questions in the tutorial and in the aspect of Providing feedback on the results of student assignments in detail. Both aspects get the same average value of 3.09. Even though these two items are in the good category, tutors must pay attention to these two aspects. Because both of these aspects are very helpful in the effectiveness of applying the tutorial.

One indicator of tutorial activities can be measured by the interaction between tutors and students, and between students and students. For that to provide opportunities for students to ask questions or opportunities to answer, it is important to be done by tutors. So, each question does not have to be answered directly by the tutor, but the tutor can provide opportunities for other students to answer the questions of their peers. As stated Marno (2009) that the habit of asking questions is one of the important factors that contribute to student success in learning achievement.

Likewise, in the aspect of providing feedback on the results of student assignments, even though the results of student assessment are already in the good category, this needs to be improved because it really helps students to know their strengths and weaknesses in learning. This will trigger students' enthusiasm in learning because students already know which competencies are mastered and which have not been learned. Sapta's research results (2012), show that giving feedback on student work results is more effective if not only in the form of grades (numbers), but also accompanied by notes or comments from tutors about the results of student assignments.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it appears that from the aspect of student assessment, the aspect of tutor performance that gets the highest score is on the aspect of assignment of assignments to students. While the

lowest value is in the aspect of providing equal opportunities for students to answer questions, and in the aspect of providing feedback on the results of student assignments.

Observations by UPBJJ-UT Ternate monitoring officers showed that all tutors had fulfilled all aspects of tutor assessment.

So, from the results of the overall data analysis, it can be concluded that the Evaluation Results of Tutor performance at UPBJJ-UT Ternate are all in good categories so it is recommended to continue assignments in the coming semester.

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